

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Transcription-Guided and Self-Supervised Speech Representations for Singing Voice Conversion

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Abstract

Singing Voice Conversion is the task of converting the timbre of a source singer to another one without modifying content or intonation. One of the main concerns when building a Singing Voice Conversion system is the type of content representations used for ensuring high intelligibility in converted voices. One approach is to use Cotatron encoder, however it has a major drawback since it requires lyrics transcriptions as input. In order not to be dependent on those transcriptions, a new area in Automatic Speech Recognition known as Self-Supervised Speech Representations seeks to extract robust latent representations from large-scale unlabeled speech corpus. A recent and popular family of such algorithms is VQ-Wav2Vec, that has been already applied to Speech Voice Conversion, however its use for Singing Voice Conversion has not been explored yet. In this master thesis, we implement a new Singing Voice Conversion using VQ-Wav2Vec features and perform a performance comparison with respect to Cotatron. We found through subjective listening tests and Word Error Rate calculation that self-supervised speech representations with VQ-Wav2Vec content features provide higher intelligibility when compared with transcription-guided content features extracted with Cotatron. In addition, singer voice similarity is slightly improved when using VQ-Wav2Vec features.

Keywords: Singing Voice Conversion; Self-Supervised Speech Representations; VQ-Wav2Vec; Cotatron

Chapter 1

Introduction

The human singing voice is an essential element in each and every culture around the world [1]. Considered by many to be the oldest musical instrument, singing voice plays an undeniable significant role in human daily life, especially as an entertainment and artistic form, but also as a way of expressing emotions and transmitting information [2, 3].

Unlike human speech, singing requires full control and awareness of the different parts of the body that define and affect the voice instrument [4]. Consequently, professional singers need to devote a considerable amount of time to vocal training every day in order to learn and improve the control of their air flow, expressiveness, intonation and diction. However, even with such a rigorous routine, there are physical constraints that limit the amount of variation a singer can produce in his or her voice, leading to unique and recognizable timbre identities for each singer. As a result, mimicking the timbre of another singer is a difficult task usually with inaccurate results [5, 6].

Despite this, recent advances in technology are now able to surpass these physical limitations in the vocal system, and thus, convert among different vocal timbres. Known in the literature as Singing Voice Conversion (SVC), this research field aims to modify a song performed by a *source* singer to sound as it was performed by another *target* singer. In other words, SVC can be understood as the task of con-

verting the voice timbre of a singer to sound as another singer without changing the original lyrics or melody. Thus, the goal is to only transfer the singer identity, keeping unaltered person-independent factors like the linguistic content, rhythm and melody [3, 5].

SVC emerged as an extension of the Voice Conversion (VC) field which is intended to convert just speech voices and, in turn, belongs to the larger field of Speech Synthesis ¹ [7]. With SVC, a wide variety of new applications appears ranging from entertainment to creative tools, such as: karaoke, games, social media, voice dubbing or even resurrecting voices from past singers [6, 8]. Another interesting and appealing use case could be using SVC as a tool for composers and music producers who want to rapidly test the suitability of their songs to different types of singers.

1.1 Motivation

Far from being just a simple algorithm, SVC needs a carefully designed architecture, usually complex and composed of many blocks aimed for different objectives. One of the most important parts of a SVC system involves dealing with the linguistic content representation, which should be fully disentangled from other singing factors like pitch and timbre, in order to provide high intelligible converted voices [9].

Assem-VC is an interesting open-source approach for VC [10] and recently adapted for SVC [11] that uses a transcription-guided content encoder known as Cotatron [12] to extract linguistic features. However, this has a major drawback: it needs lyrics transcriptions as input, which can be impractical and difficult to obtain. Moreover, audio data should be introduced in the model as short segments of 1 to 12 seconds long. Therefore, without proper annotations of phoneme duration, the manual process of segmenting each song with its corresponding lyrics can be very time consuming and cumbersome, so an automatic segmentation and lyric alignment tool becomes a major need to make the data collection process more fluid.

With the aim of getting rid of the need for lyrics transcriptions, several alterna-

¹From now on, VC will be used to refer to Voice Conversion (for speech voices), while SVC for Singing Voice Conversion (for singing voices).

tives were employed in VC and SVC based on the state-of-the-art for Automatic Speech Representation (ASR) and Text-To-Speech (TTS) tasks. One of the most recent approaches consist in using content features from self-supervised speech representation models. These type of models were pretrained with huge amounts of unlabeled speech data and they provide latent features that try to capture linguistic information [13].

A popular and recent family of such algorithms is composed of VQ-Wav2Vec [14], Wav2Vec [15] and Wav2Vec2.0 [16], all of them pretrained with huge amounts of speech data in English. From these three models, VQ-Wav2Vec has been the one that has been already applied to VC for obtaining content features in an unsupervised way with promising results [17, 18]. This model is based on the baseline Wav2Vec and incorporates discreteness, which makes it suitable for extracting ready-to-use linguistic features for a wide variety of Natural Language Processing (NLP) algorithms. However, while the VQ-Wav2Vec model has been used for VC, its use for the SVC task remains still unexplored to the best of our knowledge.

1.2 Research Questions

In this master thesis, we aim to explore the use of content features extracted from the VQ-Wav2Vec pretrained model for the SVC task. In order to analyze the suitability of these linguistic representations, we will also study the impact of using transcription-guided content features extracted from the Cotatron model, so as to compare both approaches.

Therefore, from here, we derive the following main research questions that give shape to this master thesis and that we aim to answer:

1. Can self-supervised speech representations extracted from the VQ-Wav2Vec pretrained model be used as linguistic features for the SVC task?
2. If so, what is their impact on the similarity to the target singer timbre and on the intelligibility of converted singing voices when compared with transcription-guided content features extracted from the Cotatron model?

3. Is there any difference between speech and singing voice conversion tasks in terms of intelligibility and pitch precision of converted voices when using VQ-Wav2Vec features?

For the first research question we hypothesize that, indeed, VQ-Wav2Vec self-supervised speech representations can be used for SVC just like they can be used for VC. Using English as the reference language, the reason behind this hypothesis is that VQ-Wav2Vec model is pretrained with a very large corpus of English speech data in a wide variety of situations with different phoneme durations, so we expect that they can be also successfully applied to extract content representations from singing voices in the same language.

As for the second research question, we initially hypothesize that the intelligibility will be better for the approach using Cotatron content features since it relies on lyrics transcriptions, so these linguistic features will presumably contain more accurate representations than the ones obtained from unlabeled audio samples with VQ-Wav2Vec pretrained model. In addition, Cotatron content encoder can be easily fine-tuned with singing voices, however, since only few hours of singing data are available as compared with the hundreds of hours used for training VQ-Wav2Vec, fine-tuning with singing voices does not seem like an option to further improve VQ-Wav2Vec in the SVC context. Therefore, we initially hypothesize that Cotatron will be more accurate for extracting content features from singing voices. With respect to the singer similarity, we expect both approaches to provide similar results, since in theory both Cotatron and VQ-Wav2Vec solely focus on providing linguistic features, disentangled from singer identity. However we will check and compare through listening tests the ability of each approach to disentangle content from other aspects of the singing voice that may be linked to singer identity.

Finally, for the third research question, we hypothesize that the intelligibility will be better for the VC task, since the VQ-Wav2Vec model was pretrained only with speech data. As for the pitch matching, we hypothesize that it will be also better for the VC task. The reason behind this hypothesis is that because singing voices cover

a wider frequency range than speech, the VQ-Wav2Vec model will probably find it more difficult to extract fully disentangled linguistic representations from audio data with more frequency variation, so these representations will probably contain some pitch information as well, which would damage the final converted pitch.

1.3 Contributions

Taking as a reference the previous research questions, this master thesis has the following main contributions:

1. Implementation of a new off-line any-to-one² SVC and VC system using VQ-Wav2Vec speech representations as content features under female-to-male and male-to-female scenarios.
2. Implementation of a new off-line any-to-one SVC system using Cotatron content features under female-to-male and male-to-female scenarios, and implementation of the tool proposed in [19] that performs semi-automatic segmentation and lyrics alignment for Cotatron data preparation.
3. Performance comparison in terms of singer similarity and intelligibility in converted voices using Cotatron vs. using VQ-Wav2Vec content features.
4. Performance comparison in terms of intelligibility and pitch mismatching for speech vs. singing voice conversion using VQ-Wav2Vec content features.

1.4 Structure of the Report

The remainder of this master thesis report is structured as follows. First, in Chapter 2 we present the state-of-the-art for SVC that is relevant to this master thesis with special focus on the encoding of linguistic features. Then, in Chapter 3 we explain the overall architecture used in this master thesis for performing SVC, with the two

²Any-to-one means that any arbitrary source singer voice can be transformed to only one target. In other words, the system is trained for only one target voice, but any unseen voice can act as source.

different baseline approaches, one using VQ-Wav2Vec features and the another one using Cotatron features.

After this, in Chapter 4 we describe the datasets used as well as other data preparation aspects that were important to ensure a good starting point for training the algorithms. Next, we explain in Chapter 5 the experiments carried out, the evaluation framework used as well as the results of such experiments.

To end this report, in Chapter 6 we discuss the results in more depth and connect them to the research questions introduced in Section 1.2. Lastly, in Chapter 7 we extract and summarize the main findings from this master thesis, and we also give an overview of the limitations of this study and provide insights for future work.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

Research on VC has been experiencing a very prolific period in the last years. Similarly, as a response to these advances in VC and in Singing Voice Synthesis, SVC has been progressively growing and recently gaining more and more attention from researchers, also driven by the appealing applications that could be explored with this technology [5, 6].

However, compared with VC, there are some special considerations that need to be addressed when it comes to SVC. In VC, speech prosody is generally considered to contain information of speaker characteristics, hence pitch information is typically expected to change when converting from one speech voice to another [5, 20]. However, when dealing with singing voices, the prosodic information is given by the music score, so it is not specific to the singer and does not need to be transferred. Therefore, singer identity needs to be disentangled from pitch in SVC, and in addition a wider frequency range and musical expressions such as vibrato have to be dealt with [5, 21, 22].

Several criteria can be used to study and classify the proposed SVC architectures which, indeed, are typically based on previous efforts in VC. The most basic classifications refer to: (1) the type of data used (parallel or non-parallel), (2) whether they are based on statistical methods or deep learning and (3) whether they are intended for real-time or off-time use.

On the one hand, parallel data approaches require the same linguistic content for both source and target singer, i.e. lyrics alignment between both singers should be possible. However, while these systems are able to obtain high performance, they pose a significant drawback: the need to collect parallel training data, which can be very challenging especially in real life applications. On the other hand, non-parallel data approaches do not need such alignment between source and target voices, i.e. they can convey different linguistic content. Therefore, they are much more practical and flexible, and recently have shown comparable or even superior performance to parallel data systems [23].

While initial contributions in SVC relied on statistical approaches with parallel data [22, 24], in the last years the spectacular progress of deep learning, especially on Natural Language Processing, has led to a paradigm shift in VC and SVC: deep learning architectures with non-parallel data, which considerably outperform previous statistical methods in terms of voice quality and naturalness [7].

Furthermore, the majority of SVC systems are only intended for off-line use, meaning that the conversion process during inference phase is done after recording a specific vocal segment. However, there is recently an increasing interest on developing SVC algorithms that can be used in real-time scenarios. Although still a nascent area, real-time SVC poses several challenges, especially as a result of the computational load associated with the complex deep learning architectures, which increases latency. Despite this, some approaches like [25] are specifically intended for real-time use, although the overall quality is apparently affected by the use of lightweight models and the code is not released as open-source.

In this master thesis we will focus on SVC using deep learning with non-parallel data and for off-line use.

2.1 Typical Structure of a SVC System

Most of the VC and SVC systems rely on a three-stage structure based on: feature extraction, mapping and reconstruction [7], as illustrated in the workflow schema

of Figure 1. Recently, there has also been increasing interest in end-to-end VC and SVC approaches which, instead of relying on these three steps, train one model that jointly performs the conversion and directly generates the resultant waveform [25, 26]. However, these models are much more unstable and generally harder to train, so in this master thesis we will focus on a classical three-stage procedure.

Figure 1: Typical 3-stage workflow in SVC architectures.

Feature extraction

Feature extraction refers to the steps needed to obtain person-independent factors, like linguistic content and pitch information. This is generally done with specific algorithms or networks to extract each acoustic feature followed by separate encoders, essentially a content encoder and an intonation encoder. Additionally, some authors also include a loudness or amplitude encoder for improved performance in converted voices [21, 25].

In Section 2.1.1 we explain in more detail the different approaches proposed in the literature for the content representation, since this is the main topic of this master thesis project. As for the intonation encoder, this is typically done with an algorithm that extracts fundamental frequency (F0) followed by a small neural network to produce latent intonation features.

Mapping

Mapping refers to the conversion function that transforms features from the source voice to features of the target voice. This conversion function can be obtained with different types of architectures. A typical approach is to use an autoregressive decoder conditioned by some type of embedding of the target singer voice, which

takes features (e.g. content, intonation, loudness) as input and produces a mel spectrogram as the output [11, 27, 28].

Generative models have recently become a popular option for the conversion module like Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN) architectures [5, 6, 29]. However, GANs typically suffer from instability during training. A robust and recent alternative is using diffusion probability based acoustic models like DiffSinger [30], which are an interesting option with very good performance [3]. In this master thesis we use a denoising diffusion probabilistic model as the acoustic model that performs the conversion stage, as we will later explain in Chapter 3.

Reconstruction

Reconstruction is the process of going from converted features or mel spectrograms to a final waveform. This is generally achieved via a vocoder network. A common approach in SVC is to use hand-designed vocoders like WORLD [31] for synthesis of the voice –and also for extracting features during acoustic modelling– since they explicitly separate pitch from timbre components [5, 6, 27, 29].

However, neural network-based vocoders are recently a popular choice for the back-end of VC and SVC since they can generate higher-quality audio. In addition, adversarial waveform generation is used in several works like [23, 3, 11], with GAN-based vocoders like HiFi-GAN [32].

2.1.1 Content Encoder

One of the main challenges in VC and SVC is to obtain a representation of the linguistic content that is fully disentangled from other features like timbre and F0, and at the same time, that provides enough information about content so that the converted voice can be highly intelligible. In some approaches, the content representations are extracted jointly by constraining the mapping module, while in other proposals they are obtained from specific content modules.

To the first category belongs [33, 28], which jointly train a content encoder and the

mapping module with an auto-encoder network in an end-to-end fashion. These models extract content information in an unsupervised way and use adversarial training. Another strategy but less common, is to simply use spectral features extracted from the WORLD vocoder as inputs to a GAN model which performs the mapping function, preserving the content information using identity mapping loss [5, 6].

A more common strategy is to have a separate content encoder. Within this second category we can find several types of approaches for content representation. On the one hand, we have transcription-guided systems like [12] and [34] which propose Cotatron and Mellotron encoders, respectively. Both are based on multispeaker Tacotron 2 architecture [35] and generate lyrics alignments that can be used as linguistic features for an acoustic model. However, a major disadvantage is that this type of content encoders need lyrics transcriptions as input.

On the other hand, a more explored line of algorithms within this second category takes advantage of pretrained ASR models to extract content features. Relying on the so-called Phonetic Posteriorgrams (PPGs), these features are robust content embeddings extracted from the last layers of ASR models pretrained with large-scale speech corpus with various recording environments, background noise, accent and pitch. The most common ASR models used to extract PPGs are based on Deep Feedforward Sequential Memory Networks (DFSMN), like in [3, 36]. However, while PPGs are very robust for VC, they can be insufficient to encode rich linguistic features that would be needed for SVC, and they still limit the style and naturalness of singing voices in a noticeable way [23, 12].

A new related research area in NLP aims to extract the so-called self-supervised speech representations from raw audio, with some contributions already proposed for obtaining content representations in VC [18, 17]. As opposed to PPGs, these models are pretrained in a self-supervised fashion, thus without any speech annotations. Although still a nascent area, self-supervised speech representations are gaining more and more attention in recent years. The goal of these models is to learn speech representations in a similar way to how children learn their first language,

leveraging self-supervised learning methods with unlabeled audio data [13].

To this class of models belongs HuBERT [37], whose use for SVC has recently been explored in [23]. Among the other different ASR models in this area, there is a well-known family of three algorithms proposed by Facebook AI Research which consist in: Wav2Vec, VQ-Wav2Vec and Wav2Vec 2.0. They are based on convolutional architectures with contrastive loss, and have not been explored for SVC yet.

Let's now delve into more details of the two types of content representations that will be used and compared in this master thesis: Cotatron and VQ-Wav2Vec.

Cotatron

Cotatron is an open-source linguistic feature extractor that jointly learns how to predict (1) the alignment between mel spectrogram and text transcription and (2) the next mel spectrogram, using as inputs the previous mel frames, the lyrics transcription and the speaker/singer representation:

$$\hat{M}_{1:i}, A_i = Decoder_{TTS}(Encoder_{text}(T), M_{0:i-1}, z^{id})$$

where T, M, A, z^{id} are the text, log mel spectrogram, alignment and speaker representation, respectively. The Cotatron architecture is based on an encoder-decoder network that incorporates the attention mechanism [38]. There are two encoders: a text encoder ($Encoder_{text}$) and a speaker encoder, and an autoregressive decoder ($Decoder_{TTS}$) that is teacher forced to improve the alignment learning [12]¹. The outputs of the Cotatron system are linguistic features L that are computed from the multiplication of the resultant alignment by the encoded text:

$$L = matmul(A, Encoder_{text}(T))$$

The overall Cotatron architecture contains around 16.8 million parameters and it is depicted in Figure 2.

¹Teacher forcing refers to a mechanism for efficient training in Recurrent Neural Networks that uses the ground truth from a previous timestep as input, instead of using the model output at that previous timestep

Figure 2: Diagram of Cotatron architecture.

VQ-Wav2Vec

VQ-Wav2Vec [14] model is based on the original implementation called Wav2Vec [15], which is composed of an encoder network $f : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Z}$ that produces latent representations with causal convolutions, and a context or aggregator network $g : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$ that outputs contextualized representations. This aggregator combines many encoder timesteps into a new value for each timestep [14]. The model is trained with the aim of minimizing the contrastive loss \mathcal{L}_k for each timestep k ².

VQ-Wav2Vec keeps the same structure as Wav2Vec with the difference that it adds a discretization layer between the encoder and the aggregator, known as quantization module, $q : \mathcal{Z} \rightarrow \hat{\mathcal{Z}}$, so now the aggregator uses the discrete representation as an input, $g : \hat{\mathcal{Z}} \rightarrow \mathcal{C}$. In a similar fashion to the approach in [21], that uses a Vector Quantized VAE (VQVAE) to get discrete linguistic features, VQ-Wav2Vec introduces discreteness which makes it lightweight (around 35 million parameters) and faster than its predecessor Wav2Vec. The quantization module uses Gumbel-Softmax for approximating the argmax function in a differentiable way in order to get a one-hot representation. Moreover, VQ-Wav2Vec has been shown to be the best self-supervised speech representation model for VC in the any-to-one scenario [39], but it has not been explored for SVC yet.

²The mathematical details can be checked in the original publication [14]

Figure 3: The Wav2Vec family. Diagrams from [15, 14, 16].

Lastly, Wav2Vec 2.0 [16] further improves Wav2Vec by including the discretized indices of VQ-Wav2Vec and by modifying the context network with a transformer architecture that shows better performance. However, it must be taken into account that its non-causal architecture together with the huge amount of parameters (up to 317 million) makes it probably not a very attractive option for SVC with real-time performance. Still, in this master thesis we deal with off-line SVC, however we only focus on VQ-Wav2Vec, leaving the exploration of Wav2Vec and Wav2Vec 2.0 models for SVC as future work. Figure 3 shows an schematic illustration of each of the three models: Wav2Vec, VQ-Wav2Vec and Wav2Vec 2.0.

Chapter 3

System Overview

Although the focus of this master thesis is on the linguistic content representation, namely on the use of VQ-Wav2Vec features and how it compares to the use of Cotatron features, we need a complete SVC architecture to make the overall system work. Following the three-stage approach described in Chapter 2, the architecture, apart from the content encoder, needs an additional intonation encoder, an acoustic model to perform the conversion stage and a vocoder to transform the converted mel spectrogram into an audible waveform.

In the literature, Cotatron is used in VC and SVC as part of a recent architecture known as Assem-VC [10, 11]. This architecture, intended for any-to-many conversion ¹, encodes the different acoustic dimensions (i.e. lyrics, pitch, timbre) in interpretable formats, which allows for easier control. As well as encoding linguistic content with Cotatron, it encodes pitch using fundamental frequency detection and uses a decoder based on the one used in Cotatron architecture. An schematic view of the Assem-VC architecture for the SVC task is shown in Figure 4.

The initial idea was to use the available open-source implementation of Assem-VC architecture for VC and adapt it for SVC as described in [11]. However, after dedicating time to this task and coming up with the SVC adaptation of Assem-

¹Any-to-many means that any arbitrary source singer voice can be transformed to many target singers that have seen during training.

Figure 4: Schematic view of Assem-VC architecture.

VC, the results were not convincing enough in terms of voice quality. Therefore, we decided to move on with a different architecture which provided better results at first glance. This architecture is composed of modules that were available as part of my internship at VoctroLabs [40] while working on this master thesis. As a result, the code is not to be released as open-source, since some fundamental blocks are proprietary of VoctroLabs. The data used for training the models are also proprietary as we will explain later in Chapter 4.

Overall, the system follows a classic three-stage style structure, namely: feature extraction, acoustic model and vocoder. Two different baseline architectures are used, one using VQ-Wav2Vec features (Figure 5) and another using Cotatron features (Figure 6). Both approaches only differ in the content representation module in order to make the most fair comparison between them. In addition, for the speech experiments that will be described in Chapter 5, we use the exact same architecture, even with the F0 detection in the feature extraction stage, which is not typical in VC. We decided to keep the same architecture to better isolate the effects of the content representation module, and also to later compare how well converted voices follow the source pitch for speech and singing voices.

3.1 Feature extraction

In addition to the content features, intonation features are extracted using a proprietary algorithm by VoctroLabs which is specifically intended for singing voices. In addition, loudness features are obtained using the open-source *pyloudnorm* library

Figure 5: Schematic view of the proposed architecture using VQ-Wav2Vec features.

Figure 6: Schematic view of the proposed architecture using Cotatron features.

[41]. Content features, intonation features and loudness features enter separate encoders before being fed into the acoustic model.

The encoder for the content features consists in a sequence of four 1D convolutional layers intercalated with Leaky ReLu activation functions. The first convolutional layer has a kernel size of 5 and the rest have kernel size of 3, and all of them have 256 output channels. In the case of the intonation encoder, it consists of a simple 1D convolutional layer with a kernel size of 9. Lastly, the loudness encoder is formed by two 1D convolutional layers, the first one with kernel size of 9 and 18 output channels, and the second one with kernel size of 1 and 256 output channels.

The outputs of these three encoders is summed and fed to a diffusion-based acoustic model. Let’s now see in more detail how the linguistic features are obtained for each of the two baseline models.

3.1.1 Self-Supervised Content Features Using VQ-Wav2Vec

The pretrained VQ-Wav2Vec model available through the *fairseq* library [42] is used in order to get self-supervised content features from the raw audio, as represented in Figure 5.

In particular, the discrete indices are extracted from the VQ-Wav2Vec model pretrained on the LibriSpeech ASR Corpus, which contains approximately 1000 hours of 16 *kHz* English speech [43]. The model implementation uses Gumbel-Softmax algorithm.

3.1.2 Transcription-Guided Content Features Using Cotatron

The open-source implementation of Cotatron was used to extract linguistic features in a transcription-guided way as illustrated in Figure 6. As it will be explained in Chapter 5, in order to adapt the Cotatron architecture for the 200 *Hz* frame rate required by the SVC system, we trained Cotatron from scratch for a sampling rate of 32 *kHz* using the LibriTTS train-clean-100 split [44] –with 100 hours derived from LibriSpeech Corpus– and VCTK Corpus [45] –approximately 44 hours of English speech– as detailed in the original paper [12].

Then, fine-tuning with our singing datasets was performed as it will be later detailed in Chapter 5. In addition, transcriptions were collected for each audio file with the help of a semi-automatic lyrics alignment tool, as we will present in Chapter 4.

3.2 Diffusion-Based Decoder

The acoustic model used for the conversion stage is based on a denoising diffusion probabilistic model. This model is proprietary of VoctroLabs, similar the open-source DiffSinger model [30].

DiffSinger model is a robust diffusion-based acoustic model that addresses the over-smoothing and unstable training problems of other previous approaches. Diffusion models have shown very promising results in image generation and are recently

adapted to the audio domain, with also very good results. They are based on two processes: diffusion and reverse (or denoising). On the one hand, the diffusion process consists in a Markov chain with fixed parameters that converts input data into an isotropic Gaussian distribution by gradually adding Gaussian noise. On the other hand, the reverse or denoising process is another Markov chain implemented as a neural network that learns to restore again the data converted by the diffusion process [30].

The diffusion-based model used in this master thesis is intended for any-to-one use. Therefore, only the audio files of the target singer are used to train the diffusion decoder, which learns to replicate realistic mel spectrograms from the input audios of the target. Then, on the inference phase, any source audio from any arbitrary singer can be used as input to get content, F0 and loudness features that will be fed into the diffusion decoder. The already trained diffusion decoder will be able to produce mel spectrograms from the content, pitch and loudness of the source singer but with the identity of the target singer that was used to train it.

3.3 Non-Autoregressive Neural Vocoder

Finally, the converted mel spectrograms coming from the diffusion-based decoder are transformed into audible waveforms with the neural vocoder proposed in [46]. This model is characterized by its non-autoregressive nature as well as being based on a quite constrained source-filter model of speech production. It is similar to conventional parametric vocoders like WORLD [31] with various signal processing blocks replaced by neural networks ².

²For more details on this vocoder, check "Chapter 6: Non-autoregressive source-filter neural vocoder" in the original publication [46].

Chapter 4

Datasets

As it is widely known, in order to ensure a good starting point, every model based on deep neural networks needs a great amount of data with great quality. As a result, in this master thesis, a lot of time was exclusively devoted to data preparation. In this Chapter we detail the most important aspects that were considered in relation to data.

One of the reasons why VC is much more explored than SVC lie on the lack of open-source singing datasets. In fact, only two open-source singing datasets are suitable for the SVC task: NUS-48E with 48 English songs performed by 12 singers [47], and the Children’s Song Dataset (CSD) with 50 English songs performed by a Korean female singer [48]. The scarcity of more open-source singing datasets leads to more and more researchers relying on proprietary datasets.

As part of my internship at VoctroLabs during the course of this master thesis, I had access to proprietary acapella datasets of professional singers. These datasets were used to train and test the baseline models. In addition, having data from male and female singers, we decided to study the performance of such models for gender conversion scenarios, namely female-to-male and male-to-female use cases.

The generic information about the singing and speech datasets used in this master thesis is depicted in Table 1. Four different datasets were employed, two correspond-

ing to a male singer and a female singer, and two corresponding to a male speaker and a female speaker. All the datasets are in English.

Table 1: Datasets used in this master thesis.

Type	Gender	Duration	Songs/Sentences
Singing	Female	4h 11min	500 sentences with different melodies
Singing	Male	2h 1min	57 pop-rock songs
Speech	Female	4h 7min	1608 sentences with 5 different emotions
Speech	Male	1h 50min	1632 sentences with 4 different emotions

4.1 Data Preparation

In order to use the datasets previously described, segmentation of the full recordings was necessary for batch optimization. Especially, in the case of Cotatron and following the indications made by the authors [12], we ensured that audio segments were 1 to 12 seconds long. These segments should be selected so as the lyrics in each segment form sentences that do not contain interrupted words (i.e. segments do not cut individual words), so as to collect consistent text transcriptions.

4.1.1 Semi-Automatic Segmentation of Lyrics

Three of the datasets were already segmented and only some corrections and manual annotations for the lyrics were needed. However, for the female singer, the segmentation and lyrics annotation was done from scratch with the help of the segmentation tool described in [19]. The above mentioned segmentation algorithm is based on two consecutive processes: (1) waveform splitting and (2) recognition and matching.

First, in order to split the original waveform, the initial and final silences were removed after computing the waveform energy. Next, intermediate silences are found setting an duration and energy threshold –the last one depends on the loudness of the original waveform–. In this case, only intermediate silences longer than 0.5 seconds were considered in order to place the boundary between two segments. We also added, as suggested in [19] a small silence at the beginning and end of each

segment, and constrained the search of intermediate silences so as we ended up obtaining segments of 1 to 12 seconds long.

After having all the segments, which is done in a fully automatic way, we performed manual revision of the resultant segments to ensure that the original audio files were successfully trimmed. The next phase consist in obtaining the lyrics transcription of each segment. We manually collected the overall transcripts for the full original waveforms, and used the Google text-to-speech API package in Python [49] as indicated in [19] to extract the lyrics for each segment. Then, the five top transcriptions for each segment were compared to the full lyrics collected manually using a sliding window with variable size starting from the length of the ASR transcription, and using the Levenshtein distance. The segment from the full lyrics whose score was the highest when computing the Levenshtein distance with the ASR transcription was selected as the lyrics transcription for the segment ¹. After getting all the transcriptions for all the segments, we again checked the validity of each one and corrected errors. A schematic diagram of the whole segmentation and lyrics alignment process is depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Diagram of algorithm for semi-automatic audio segmentation and alignment of lyrics, based on [19].

Finally, before introducing the text transcripts as input to the Cotatron model, the raw text is converted to ARPABET format using the grapheme-to-phoneme algorithm provided in the open-source implementation of Cotatron [12].

¹Go to [19] for more details about the algorithm using the Levenshtein distance

Chapter 5

Experiments and Results

In this Chapter we present and explain the experiments carried out, the evaluation procedures used and the results obtained.

5.1 Experiments

Overall, for this master thesis six different models ¹ were trained using the two baseline architectures outlined in Chapter 3. Since we are tackling an any-to-one use case, the diffusion-based decoder is trained using only data from the target singer intended for each experiment. However, although the experiments are valid for any-to-one scenario, we performed one-to-one tests using the data from the available singer with the opposite gender as the source singer.

In particular, four models were trained for the SVC task, namely: two for the VQ-Wav2Vec approach –one for the male singer as target, and another for the female singer as target–, and two for the Cotatron approach –one for the same male singer as target, and another for the same female singer as target–. The two remaining experiments correspond to the VQ-Wav2Vec approach for the VC task using in one of them the male speaker as target, and the female speaker as target for the another one. A summary of the different experiments carried out can be seen in Table 2.

¹Since we use a pretrained vocoder, when we speak of trained models we refer to the diffusion-based decoder together with the feature encoders.

Table 2: Experiments carried out in this master thesis.

#	Task	Content Features	Source	Target
1	SVC	VQ-Wav2Vec	Female singer	Male singer
2	SVC	Cotatron	Female singer	Male singer
3	SVC	VQ-Wav2Vec	Male singer	Female singer
4	SVC	Cotatron	Male singer	Female singer
5	VC	VQ-Wav2Vec	Female speaker	Male speaker
6	VC	VQ-Wav2Vec	Male speaker	Female speaker

The hyperparameters for computing mel spectrograms, extracting F0 and training the diffusion-based model are common for all the experiments and are shown in Table 3. The vocoder that we used is pretrained and generates waveforms with sampling rate of 32 kHz . Therefore, a hop size of 160 samples (hop time multiplied by sampling rate) results in a frame rate of 200 Hz (sampling rate divided by hop size) as a reference for the whole system.

VQ-Wav2Vec features were directly extracted from raw audio downsampled to 16 kHz using the pretrained model available at *fairseq* library, as commented in Chapter 3. Since VQ-Wav2Vec features are extracted with a sampling rate of 16 kHz and a hop size of 160 samples, this leads to a frame rate of 100 Hz . In order to adapt it to the 200 Hz frame rate required in our system, we just repeat each element in the VQ-Wav2Vec vector twice.

In the case of the Cotatron approach, since the original pretrained version is available for 22.05 kHz , we had to train Cotatron from scratch for a sampling rate of 32 kHz . In order to do so, we first followed the indications in [12], initially training with the *train-clean-100* split of LibriTTS for $25k$ steps, and then adding VCTK Corpus and training with both datasets for another $20k$ steps. All the audios of these speech datasets were resampled to 32 kHz before training Cotatron. Then, a fine-tuning step with singing voices was performed. We used both the female and male singing datasets and fine-tuned for $40k$ steps. The whole Cotatron training process was done using one GPU and it took approximately three days.

For each of the six diffusion models, we used all the data available from the correspondent target singer in order to train them. As for the validation data, we used approximately 250 files from the correspondent source singer for each experiment. Each model was trained for $2M$ steps and using 1 GPU, which took about 2 days for each experiment.

Table 3: Hyperparameters for feature extraction and training the diffusion model.

Hyperparameter	Value
Sampling rate	32 kHz
Hop time	5 ms
Window time	45 ms
Window type	Hanning
FFT size	1440
Number of mel bands	100
Batch size	24
Optimization algorithm	AdamW, 0.001 weight decay

5.2 Evaluation and Results

Once all the models were trained it was time to evaluate and compare them. Going back to the research questions that were posed in Chapter 1.2, we are interested in comparing VQ-Wav2Vec and Cotatron approaches for the SVC task in terms of both singer voice similarity –how similar the converted voices are to the timbre of the target singer– and intelligibility –how well the lyrics can be understood in the converted voices–. We are also interested in evaluating and comparing the intelligibility and pitch matching –how well the pitch of the converted voice matches the pitch of the source voice– between VC and SVC tasks using VQ-Wav2Vec features.

5.2.1 Subjective Listening Test

In the literature for VC and SVC listening tests are typically employed given the intrinsic subjectiveness of this type of evaluations. In this master thesis we created

a listening test to evaluate both singer voice similarity and intelligibility. In order to do so, we used the MULTiple Stimuli with Hidden Reference and Anchor (MUSHRA) methodology [50] inspired by its popularity in state-of-the-art Voice Synthesis publications [51, 52, 53, 54]. One important advantage of using MUSHRA over classical Mean Opinion Score tests is that all the systems being evaluated can be presented at the same time in one panel, which makes it easier to discriminate and compare them [53].

Listening test Cotatron vs VQ-Wav2Vec

Thanks for your interest in participating in the listening test. The overall test will roughly take 15 minutes. Please take the time and carefully rate every item.

Instructions:

- Most important: use high quality studio headphones and a good soundcard!
- Listen through all test files and test sets before you do any ratings to get used to the material.
- In the first section you will have to rate singer similarity: how similar the timbre of each singer in the test audios is to the reference one in the top.
- In the last section you will have to rate intelligibility: how well you understand the text using as a reference the audio and the sentence on the top.
- Try to rate the overall impression of a test item and don't concentrate on single aspects.

Available HTML5 browser features: [WebAudioAPI](#), [BlobAPI](#), [WAV](#), [FLAC](#), [Vorbis](#), [MP3](#), [AAC](#)
This listening test has been created with [BeagleJS master](#).

Figure 8: Initial panel of the MUSHRA test describing the instructions.

In a MUSHRA listening test there is a reference audio on the top of each test panel. This reference audio will be used to assess each of the test items that appear right below and that should be rated. In a typical MUSHRA test, as well as rating the items from the systems that we want to evaluate, we include the reference again and one or two anchor items that allow to have a wider range of discrimination and therefore, make the rating process easier. In addition, the positions of the items are randomised in each panel so that their order does not become predictable. Subjects of the MUSHRA test can rate each item with a continuous slider from 0 to 100. The following labels are shown on top of the different slides for facilitating the rating

process: Bad (0-20), Poor (21-40), Fair (41-60), Good (61-80), Excellent (81-100).

We designed the MUSHRA listening test using the open-source BeagleJS tool [55]. The test contains 20 test panels, 10 of them evaluating singer voice similarity, and the remaining 10 evaluating intelligibility. Subjects entering the test were first presented with the panel shown in Figure 8 describing the instructions. In test panels 1 to 5, subjects were asked to rate singer voice similarity with respect to a reference male singer for 5 test items, corresponding to the female-to-male experiments. In test panels 6 to 10, the same was done but now with a female reference voice, corresponding to the male-to-female experiments. The reference voice was chosen from audios of the original male and female singers used to train the respective models. Within the test items we included the following:

1. **Experiment 1 (panels 1-5) and experiment 3 (panels 6-10):** converted voice using VQ-Wav2Vec-based approach.
2. **Experiment 2 (panels 1-5) and experiment 4 (panels 6-10):** converted voice using Cotatron-based approach.
3. **Reference:** the same identical audio as the original reference in the top of the test panel.
4. **Anchor 1:** another audio from the original singer.
5. **Anchor 2:** the original source singer audio but pitch shifted to sound closer to the opposite gender.

For creating Anchor 2, we used the Pitch Shift effect of version 2.4.2 of Audacity(R) [56]. The idea was to modify the source audio to sound more like the gender of the reference. This effect slightly changes the timbre when it shifts the pitch of the voice up and down. The resultant voice suits better with the remaining test items than the original source voices and, because it should be the test item with the worst singer similarity, it can be used to have a reference for a low rating score in singer similarity. Anchor 2 together with the converted voices from the VQ-Wav2Vec and

Cotatron experiments, were derived from the same source audios. In order to select Anchor 1 and the reference audios, we made sure that they had a similar voice range and voice style to the converted audios, so that the comparison would be more fair. A panel of our MUSHRA listening test evaluating singer similarity can be seen in Figure 9.

The screenshot shows a web-based interface for a MUSHRA listening test. The main heading is "Rate singer similarity (1 of 20)". Below this, there is a "Reference" audio player with "Play" and "Stop" buttons, followed by five rating categories: "Bad", "Poor", "Fair", "Good", and "Excellent". Each category is represented by a vertical line on a horizontal scale. Below the reference are five "Test Item" rows, each with a "Play" and "Stop" button and a corresponding horizontal rating scale. At the bottom of the interface, there are "Previous Test" and "Next Test" buttons, a timer showing "00:00", a progress bar, checkboxes for "Loop" and "Auto Return", and a "Volume" control. A small text note at the bottom right states: "Available HTML5 browser features: WebAudioAPI, BlobAPI, WAV, FLAC, Vorbis, MP3, AAC. This listening test has been created with BeagleJS master."

Figure 9: Example panel of the MUSHRA listening test evaluating singer similarity.

In the second part of the MUSHRA listening test we evaluated intelligibility. In these test panels, subjects were asked to rate intelligibility for 10 different sentences: 5 for female-to-male conversions and 5 for male-to-female conversion. In each test panel, a unique sentence was evaluated, whose transcription was provided in the heading of the question. The reference audio was an original singing voice, female for test panels 11 to 15 and male for panels 16 to 20. The test items included the following:

1. **Experiment 1 (panels 11-15) and experiment 3 (panels 16-20):** converted singing voice using VQ-Wav2Vec-based approach.

Figure 10: Example panel of the MUSHRA listening test evaluating intelligibility.

2. **Experiment 2 (panels 11-15) and experiment 4 (panels 16-20)**: converted singing voice using Cotatron-based approach.
3. **Experiment 5 (panels 11-15) and experiment 6 (panels 16-20)**: converted speech voice using VQ-Wav2Vec-based approach. In order to have the same sentences pronounced as in singing, we used custom male and female voices as source and then converted them. These custom audios were obtained recording the same sentences uttered as in the singing audios.
4. **Reference**: the same identical audio as the original reference in the top of the test panel.
5. **Speech Anchor 1**: we selected as anchor the converted speech voice corresponding to female-to-female or male-to-male conversions for panels 11-15 and 16-20, respectively.

A panel of our MUSHRA listening test evaluating intelligibility can be seen in Figure 10. The overall listening test with 20 test panels took between 15 to 20 minutes, and gathered a total of 18 participants, all of them with engineering or computer science backgrounds.

After collecting all the singer voice similarity and intelligibility scores, we visualized the results in the form of boxplots. Figure 11 shows the boxplots for the singer voice similarity scores, and Figure 12 for the intelligibility scores.

Figure 11: MUSHRA singer voice similarity scores.

5.2.2 Objective Evaluation of Intelligibility

Since the subjective evaluation of intelligibility could lead to ambiguous responses, we also added an objective evaluation method to compute the Word Error Rate (WER) for each of the experiments. In order to do so, we initially tried the Google text-to-speech API [49] already used in the lyrics alignment task (detailed in Chapter 4). We also tried the AWS Transcribe tool [57]. Since both ASR tools were not trained with singing voices, we did not initially expect good results, however the AWS Transcribe tool produced very accurate transcription of the original singing audio files. We used the same audio files that were included in the listening test for obtaining the transcriptions and computing the WER. The library *jiwer* was

Figure 12: MUSHRA intelligibility scores.

employed to compute the WER using the Levenshtein distance. Results are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Word Error Rate computed with transcriptions from AWS Transcribe.

Task	Model	Gender	WER (%)
SVC	Original singing	Original Female	2.56
SVC	VQ-Wav2Vec	Converted Male	17.95
SVC	Cotatron	Converted Male	34.35
VC	Original speech	Original Female	0.0
VC	VQ-Wav2Vec speech	Converted Male	17.02
SVC	Original singing	Original Male	6.90
SVC	VQ-Wav2Vec	Converted Female	25.51
SVC	Cotatron	Converted Female	53.10
VC	Original speech	Original Male	13.80
VC	VQ-Wav2Vec speech	Converted Female	66.20

5.2.3 Objective Evaluation of Pitch Mismatch

Finally, pitch mismatch was also computed as a way to evaluate and compare how many semitones in average does the converted voice differ from the source voice in SVC and VC tasks. For doing that, we just simply used the F0 detection algorithm that was included in the main architecture explain in Chapter 3, and extracted F0 from both source and converted voices, then calculated pitch mismatching by just averaging the absolute value of the difference between both F0 sequence values computed for each pair of audio files. A total of 250 audio files were used for the calculation.

As well as getting the average pitch mismatching value in Hz , we also computed the number of differing semitones as follows:

$$\frac{|f0_s - f0_c|}{|2^{\frac{q}{12}} f0_s - f0_s|}$$

where $f0_s$ and $f0_c$ is the F0 from the source audio and converted audio, respectively; and $q = +1$ when $f0_c \geq f0_s$ and $q = -1$ when $f0_c < f0_s$. Results are shown in Table 5

Table 5: Pitch mismatch in SVC and VC experiments with VQ-Wav2Vec.

Task	Conversion	Pitch mismatch (Hz)	Pitch mismatch (semitones)
SVC	Female-to-male	7.26	0.57
VC	Female-to-male	26.57	2.32
SVC	Male-to-female	34.20	2.31
VC	Male-to-female	17.05	2.33

Chapter 6

Discussion

In this chapter, we analyze and discuss the nature of the results obtained and presented in Chapter 5.

6.1 Singer Voice Similarity

For the singer voice similarity results obtained through the MUSHRA listening test and shown in Figure 11, we can first notice that the scores for the reference audio that was present as test item are indeed very high as expected, although some values represented by diamonds fall surprisingly quite out of what would be a high score. We could attribute those scores to accidental errors or a hypothetical lack of concentration of some subjects while performing the listening test.

We can also notice that for the rest of the test items (i.e. Cotatron, VQW2V, Anchor 1 and Anchor 2) the range of the scores is very high, almost covering the entire scale. While we acknowledge that this is not optimal and reflect on the need to obtain a higher number of respondents, we also understand that evaluating singer similarity is very subjective. In fact, in this master thesis we are not evaluating the overall quality of the converted audios, since our focus was strictly on the linguistic encoding module and the quality can be greatly determined by the decoder and vocoder networks, which we are not analyzing. Therefore, many subjects could have

been influenced by the overall quality of the audio when rating the singer voice similarity, since the converted audios were probably recognizable.

As for Anchors 1 and 2, we can see in Figure 11, that the Interquartile Range (IQR) covers a high and low score area, respectively, as expected. For Anchor 1, it can be noticed that in male-to-female experiments it shows a slightly higher median, which can be interpreted as the original female singer timbre being more recognizable than the original male singer timbre for different songs. Indeed, we have to point out that for the male singer, as the data corresponds to different pop rocks songs, the vocal style considerably changes from song to song, although we tried to collect similar vocal styles in the each individual test panel.

When looking at the Cotatron and VQ-Wav2Vec boxplots, we can see that in general the VQ-Wav2Vec scores higher when comparing each type of gender conversion. Cotatron scores extend from the "fair" region to both the "good" region and "poor" region, while VQ-Wav2Vec scores are more concentrated in the "fair" and partially "good" areas. We see that the median and mean of the scores is slightly but also noticeably higher for VQ-Wav2Vec.

In addition, we can see that the female-to-male scenario was more challenging than the male-to-female, the reason behind could be simply the different amount of data of the male singer compared to the female singer. In fact, in Table 1, we can notice that the female singing dataset has twice the duration of the male singing dataset, so we consider that it is normal that the male-to-female experiments produced more satisfactory results for both Cotatron and VQ-Wav2Vec than female-to-male in terms of singer similarity. From these results we can conclude that subjectively, the VQ-Wav2Vec-based approach produced voices which, in general, were more similar to the timbre of the target voices than when using the Cotatron-based approach.

6.2 Intelligibility

For the subjective intelligibility results depicted in Figure 12, we can again notice that the singing reference was scored very high as expected, with the exception

of some isolated cases. For Anchor 1, in this case we used female-to-female or male-to-male conversions, and the results are indeed very similar to those of the speech model using VQ-Wav2Vec. However, we can infer a noticeable difference between female-to-male and male-to-female experiments, with the female-to-male scoring substantially higher. Since in this case we have more female speech data than male speech data, the reason for this difference could be the appearance of Spanish accent in the male-to-female experiments. As commented in Chapter 5, in order to have converted speech voices with the same sentences as with the singing voices, we collected female and male custom recordings with these utterances. In the case of the male speech recordings, there was a perceptible Spanish accent. This could have influenced on the subjects decision, and could be interestingly taken into account for further studies and listening tests.

For the singing experiments, we see a considerable difference between Cotatron and VQ-Wav2Vec models. Cotatron scores mainly lay on the "fair" to slightly "poor" and slightly "good" areas, while the VQ-Wav2Vec approach goes from "fair" to "good" and even slightly "excellent" intelligibility scores. As opposed to what had been hypothesized in Section 1.2, intelligibility is subjectively worse when using transcription-guided content features from Cotatron when compared with self-supervised speech representations using VQ-Wav2Vec. It is interesting to notice that while for the Cotatron approach the results are very similar between both gender conversions, in the VQ-Wav2Vec approach, the female-to-male scored particularly higher than the male-to-female scenario. This could be due to an existing trade-off between speaker/singer similarity and the preservation of original content (like linguistic and pitch information) as pointed out in [58], although more samples would be necessary to collect in order to confirm such conclusion.

When comparing VQ-Wav2Vec subjective intelligibility for singing and speech voices, we do not see a particular difference in the female-to-male scenario, with similar median and means. However, for the male-to-female scenarios, we see that the speech intelligibility is considerably worse, and the reason behind could be again the presence of Spanish accent.

In order to get a more objective measure for intelligibility, we computed the WER using the AWS Transcribe service as explained in Chapter 5. By taking a look at the results, we can notice that female-to-male experiments provided better results. Since only 15 sentences were analyzed for each gender conversion scenario, the particular selection of sentences (although random) could have affected the results. We can see that the Cotatron-based approach scores noticeably higher than the singing VQ-Wav2Vec approach, thus confirming the tendency of the subjective tests. We also see that while the speech VQ-Wav2Vec-based model scored very similar and even better than its singing counterpart in the female-to-male experiments, it radically got worse for the male-to-female scenario. Again, the presence of a foreign accent could be the reason behind. Because of lack of time, in this master thesis we could not test another male speech voices to analyze in detail the accent issues, which is left for further research.

6.3 Pitch Mismatch

The values in Table 5 for the pitch mismatch show rather inconclusive results. We see that for the female-to-male scenario the pitch mismatch is very small for the SVC task, smaller than the pitch mismatch for the VC task. However, for the male-to-female scenario we have similar results in terms of semitone mismatch. Therefore, we state that for the experiments covered in this master thesis we cannot conclude there is a significant difference in terms of pitch matching between source and converted voices when applying VQ-Wav2Vec features for SVC and VC tasks.

Chapter 7

Conclusions

In this master thesis we have implemented a new off-line any-to-one SVC system that also works for the VC scenario, that can use either VQ-Wav2Vec or Cotatron features. We have worked on the data preparation, including a semi-automatic segmentation and lyrics transcription tool, and trained six different models that were compared through subjective and objective evaluation metrics.

Going back to the original research questions, we can confirm that self-supervised speech representations extracted from the VQ-Wav2Vec pretrained model can be used as linguistic features for the SVC task. In addition, as opposed to the initial hypothesis, intelligibility is better for the VQ-Wav2Vec model than when using transcription-guided content features with the Cotatron model, both subjectively and objectively. From our listening tests we see a slight increase in singer similarity also when using the VQ-Wav2Vec content features. This suggests that self-supervised content features are more successful than transcription-guided at getting disentangled content representations.

Lastly, from our subjective tests, there was not a significant difference between VC and SVC intelligibility and pitch mismatching, except from the fact of having mixed English accents, which could have impacted the evaluation.

7.1 Limitations and Future Work

Some of the most important limitations of this master thesis that should be considered for further research are the following:

1. More subjects and more listening audios could be introduced in future listening tests.
2. Only two singers and two speakers were used. A multi-singer scenario could be explored in further research using a similar architecture.
3. In this master thesis we did not compare different vocal styles, which could be explored in future SVC research.
4. Data augmentation could be a good option to explore in SVC to counteract the lack of singing datasets.
5. Wav2Vec and Wav2Vec 2.0 content features could be also explored for SVC in future research.

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